

IReL Executive Report
2024-25

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Ireland's future depends on our ability to harness knowledge, curiosity, and collaboration. IReL plays a vital role in enabling that future - by providing researchers, educators, and students with access to world-class scholarly resources. As Minister, I am committed to strengthening our research infrastructure and ensuring that our institutions remain globally competitive, inclusive, and innovative. IReL's work is foundational to that mission, empowering discovery and driving excellence across the higher education sector.

**James Lawless TD,
Minister for Further and
Higher Education,
Research, Innovation and
Science**

Introduction from the Chair

I am delighted to introduce the IReL Executive Report for 2024–25 and to reflect on another year of progress and innovation in Ireland's national research e-library.

As Chair of the Governance Committee and President of Maynooth University, I am deeply committed to fostering a collaborative, inclusive, and forward-looking research environment. IReL's work exemplifies this spirit - supporting open access, driving innovation, and empowering researchers, educators, and students to engage meaningfully with global knowledge networks. The consortium's efforts continue to strengthen Ireland's position in the international research landscape, ensuring that our institutions remain competitive, connected, and future-ready.

Following the celebrations of IReL's 20th anniversary last year, 2024-25 has been a time of consolidation and forward momentum. IReL continues to play a central role in supporting Ireland's research ecosystem, providing seamless access to scholarly resources and advancing open research practices across our 18 member institutions. With almost 24 million recorded uses of licensed resources this year, IReL remains a cornerstone of academic life for students, researchers, and educators nationwide.

Open access remains a key priority. In 2024, IReL-supported agreements enabled the publication of over 2,800 peer-reviewed articles, further strengthening Ireland's position as a global leader in open scholarship. The National Open Access Monitor, launched earlier that year, has already proven to be a transformative tool for tracking and promoting open research outputs. Its recognition by international bodies, including UNESCO, highlights Ireland's commitment to transparency, accessibility, and innovation in research.

IReL's leadership in infrastructure development continues to grow. As the lead organisation for the Irish DataCite Consortium, IReL is helping ensure that Irish research outputs are discoverable and persistently linked. Our work to integrate researcher identifiers such as ORCID into institutional systems is also progressing, enhancing the visibility and integrity of Irish scholarship and aligning with the goals of Impact 2030.

This year also saw the successful implementation of IReL's new governance structure, including the establishment of the Advisory Committee. These committees are helping to shape IReL's strategic direction and ensure its long-term sustainability in a rapidly evolving research landscape.

IReL's journey over the past two decades has been one of growth, collaboration, and impact. As we look ahead, I am confident that IReL will continue to empower researchers, foster innovation, and support Ireland's ambition to be a global leader in open and engaged research.

I would like to extend my sincere thanks to our member institutions, strategic partners, and the dedicated IReL team for their ongoing contributions and commitment. Together, we are shaping a more connected, inclusive, and impactful research ecosystem for Ireland—one that reflects our shared values and ambitions for excellence.

Professor Eeva Leinonen, Chair, IReL Governing Committee

Director's Note

I am pleased to report that IReL continues to demonstrate its impact both in terms of usage of the resources that we provide access to, and the growth in the number of open access articles that we have supported.

The National Open Access Monitor is evidencing a growth in open access publications nationally and continues to be an international exemplar. Looking forward the Monitor will evolve to expand the type of outputs monitored as well as to start monitoring the impact of Irish open research activity.

The IReL Advisory Committee has had a very productive first year, leading the development of the IReL Mission and values, and contributing to the launch of our new Negotiation Principles. As a touchstone for the development of IReL service, projects and partnerships, the IReL Mission is foundational for planning for the future of IReL.

Inspired by the Berlin 17 Statement¹ and the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information², our Negotiation Principles were developed in consultation with the IReL community and informed by a desire to put our values at the centre of our negotiations for access to information. The Principles have improved both the clarity and transparency of our negotiation group's decision making process.

In the last twelve months we have added two new positions to the IReL Executive team with the appointment of Dr. Kyle Adams to the position of Project Support Officer and Aaron Binchy as Open Access Monitor Officer. We are delighted to have made the move to our new long-term home on Mill Street in Maynooth. Our new office affords the space needed for a growing team as well as the facilities to hold in-person and web-conference meetings. I'd like to take this opportunity to thank Maynooth University Librarian, Cathal McCauley, for his generosity in hosting the IReL office at the Library over these many years.

The next twelve months will be a period of reflection and engagement as we create a plan for the future of IReL. In 2026 the IReL Governance Committee will build on the mission development work of the IReL Advisory Committee by kicking off the process of developing our strategic plan.

We also look forward to welcoming our international peer organisations as we play host to the annual meeting of the International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC) in Autumn 2026.

Susan Reilly, Director

1. <https://oa2020.org/b17-conference/final-statement/>
2. <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>

Charting the Course for Open Access

2,730 articles were published Open Access in 2024 as part of IReL-supported OA agreements, a 7.7% increase from the 2,533 articles in 2023. 93 % of eligible authors in 2024 opted in to avail of IReL support for OA.

An additional 1,179 articles were made OA through the ScienceDirect agreement, which is led by Irish higher education librarians, with support from IReL. Measured by publications from corresponding authors affiliated with IReL member institutions, we have reached 71% OA per year, with recent trends suggesting a slow-down in that growth.

Overall we see IReL supported OA agreements continuing to be a primary driver of the NORF Action Plan's target of 100% open access to Irish research publications by 2030.

We recorded

23.9 million

uses of IReL's licensed resources in 2024

across **18 institutions**

serving over **220,000 students.**

2024
2,730
articles published

2023
2,533
articles published

IReL Reaches Milestone of 10,000 Open Access Publications

In 2025, IReL reached a major milestone in its commitment to open research and publishing transparency in enabling over 10,000 Irish research articles to be published open access, and in contributing data on them to OpenAPC. The latest data, as highlighted by this visual from OpenAPC, reveals that a total of 10,382 articles have been supported by IReL, demonstrating Ireland's commitment to open scholarship.

IReL, supported by funding from the Higher Education Authority and the Department for Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, has helped make these articles open access by negotiating 69 publishing agreements with academic publishers. Ireland's participation in these agreements and contributions to OpenAPC reflect broader international trends toward greater transparency, accessibility, and equity in academic publishing and efforts to achieve the NORF Action Plan target of charting a sustainable and inclusive course for making all Irish research publications open access by 2030.

10,382
articles have been supported by IReL

69
publishing agreements with academic publishers

For more information and to explore the data, visit OpenAPC Transformative Agreements – Ireland:
<https://treemaps.openapc.net/apcdata/transformative-agreements/#/country=IRL>

Ireland's Global Open Access Progress

IReL is proud to announce that Ireland has secured the top position in the ESAC Market Watch global Open Access (OA) rankings—a significant milestone that underscores the country's leadership in advancing open scholarship. This achievement is driven by IReL's transformative publishing agreements, which have enabled a growing number of Irish researchers to publish their work immediately as open access.

The ESAC Market Watch ranking is based on the percentage of corresponding authored papers that are made openly available at the time of publication. Ireland's #1 position reflects the success of national efforts to remove barriers to access and ensure that publicly funded research is freely available to all.

This accomplishment aligns closely with the goals of the National Open Research Forum (NORF), which envisions a sustainable and inclusive transition to 100% Open Access by 2030. IReL remains deeply committed to supporting this vision by negotiating fair and transparent agreements with publishers, advocating for researcher rights, and fostering a culture of openness across the Irish research community.

To explore the data and learn more about Ireland's standing in the global OA landscape, visit the ESAC Market Watch: https://esac-initiative.org/market-watch/#country_shares

Subscribe to Open (S2O)

SUBSCRIBE TO PEN

IReL has embraced the Subscribe to Open (S2O) model in several of its agreements. S2O is an innovative OA business model designed to transition scholarly publications from traditional subscription-based access to OA without authors or their institutions facing publication charges.

Under S2O, academic libraries continue to renew their subscriptions with the promise that, if enough libraries participate, the journal's content will be made freely accessible to all readers. So if a quota of libraries continue to subscribe, the content is made OA for everyone; if subscriptions fall below the quota, the content is not made OA, and only libraries with subscriptions can access it.

IReL Deals with S2O Elements

So far, there are a number of IReL agreements that have incorporated the S2O model. These agreements reflect IReL's commitment to advancing open access and supporting the global research community. They are aligned with the NORF Action Plan's vision of OA working on a sustainable and inclusive basis.

- American Society for Microbiology
- Annual Reviews
- Project MUSE
- Sage
- Taylor and Francis
- AIP Publishing
- American Physiological Society (APS)
- Microbiology Society

For more information on Subscribe to Open, see the [Subscribe to Open Community website](#).

“S2O offers an immediate, transparent and equitable conversion to open access, resulting in existing subscription spend having a greater impact. IReL immediately understood this, and their early adoption and support of the S2O model, which was greatly appreciated by Annual Reviews, has allowed their member institutions to align their collection budgets with their open access values, without any additional costs.”

Mark Greene, Sales & Business Development Manager, Annual Reviews

This map shows which countries have published in Annual Review's S2O journals in 2024, from any affiliation (i.e. not limited to IReL or Ireland).

“Project MUSE is delighted to announce a major achievement in its quest to advance open access. Working with IReL on the Subscribe to Open offer at the 2022 IFLA in Dublin, Aaron Binchy provided extensive feedback on our preliminary concept that led to the successful offer we presented in 2024. Thanks to the unwavering support of libraries and institutions worldwide, MUSE's Subscribe to Open (S2O) initiative has reached its sustainability goal for 2025. This remarkable accomplishment will make more than 100 journals' 2025 volumes, from 27 publishers, openly accessible on the MUSE platform.

This success reflects a collective commitment to ensuring that vital humanities and social sciences scholarship is accessible to everyone, free from paywalls. The S2O model, rooted in equity and collaboration, allows subscription journals to annually transition to open access without relying on Article Processing Charges (APCs). By leveraging MUSE's long-standing journal collections model, this initiative represents a sustainable approach to broadening access to essential scholarly works.”

Tricia Miller-Chareun, Senior Manager, Sales and Library Relations, Project MUSE

Building Community

IReL continues to strengthen its operations and strategic direction by drawing on the expertise within the IReL community.

The Governance Committee has representatives from across the university sector. The IReL Advisory Committee provides a multi-stakeholder perspective and advises the Governance Committee on strategic matters. The IReL Negotiations Group represents the best interests of the sector in vendor negotiations. IReL also has several dedicated advisory groups to help guide the development of IReL services.

As a shared service, it is important that IReL continues to engage with member institutions and gather collective insights to navigate future challenges and opportunities.

In May 2025, IReL proudly launched its Mission Statement, a reflection of our enduring commitment to advancing research excellence and impact in Ireland. The mission was shaped by the Advisory Committee and formally endorsed by the Governance Committee.

We also worked with our community to develop new Negotiation Principles, which serve to increase the transparency of decision making in IReL and ensure that IReL values are carried through in our agreements with vendors.

Mission

Mission Statement:

IReL's mission is to provide sustainable and inclusive access to scholarly communications in support of Irish research excellence and impact.

As a consortium of Irish research performing organisations and a national shared service we achieve this by:

- Providing shared access to the global scholarly network of trusted quality published information
- Supporting our authors to publish the outputs of their research openly
- Partnering locally and globally to develop an open, transparent, trusted and diverse scholarly communications ecosystem
- Responsible use of public funding and evidence-based decision making.

Our work is guided by the following values:

Negotiation Principles

In light of evolving policy and emerging international consensus, the IReL Advisory Committee also reviewed and redrafted IReL’s principles. This process has been informed not only by international discussions but also by feedback from stakeholders and the hands-on experience of the IReL Negotiation Group, who is charged with ensuring that such principles are implemented.

These renewed principles will inform IReL negotiations from 2025 onwards and help to guide the IReL Negotiations Group in deciding on where best to invest existing and finite funds.

Principles:

Cost reduction or control

Our overall aim is to achieve a fair, sustainable and affordable price for universal access that delivers value for money and cost control for our members. In some cases this will necessitate a reduction in price.

Uncapped open access

We want agreements with uncapped gold and hybrid Open Access (OA) covering 100% of our members outputs and ultimately a shift away from a per article charging model that allows all of our researchers to publish OA without author-facing charges. We are not willing to achieve this at any cost and will not invest in hybrid as a long-term strategy for achieving OA.

Transparency

We make all of our open access agreements publicly available and therefore will not agree to non-disclosure clauses. We also want publisher pricing models to be fully transparent and in the public realm. Publishers must support national efforts to monitor open access through the use of appropriate metadata.

Commitment to an OA Paradigm

Publishers should present a concrete plan to transition to OA by a set date, evidenced by data showing progression against this transition.

Equity

Publishers must demonstrate their efforts to eliminate barriers to OA publishing in low and middle income countries and reflect equity in their approach to global pricing. Recognising that we also have a role in addressing inequity by working together with publishers to reduce the environmental impact of digital scholarly communications we seek to identify measurable steps towards a reduction in the carbon footprint of this activity.

Protecting researchers’ rights

We want publishers to adopt non-exclusive licenses for OA articles and to cease trying to assert control over Author Accepted Manuscripts (AAMs) via embargo policies. Researchers must be free to exercise their rights under national and European law. Researchers must have full control over their research as well as their choice of research methods, including the application of artificial intelligence. Innovation in research must not be chilled by the threat of unlimited liability.

“IReL’s renewed negotiation principles reflect Ireland’s unwavering commitment to open, equitable, and sustainable access to research. By prioritising transparency, cost control, and the protection of researchers’ rights, IReL is not only advancing our national goals but also contributing meaningfully to the global transition toward open scholarly communication. These principles are a testament to Ireland’s leadership in shaping a research ecosystem that is inclusive, innovative, and future-focused.”

Dr Brendan Jennings, Chief Officer Research, Innovation & Engagement, Atlantic Technological University

Anchoring Scholarly Infrastructure

The Monitor currently provides data on over: **595,000 publications**

detailing publications from 2007 to the present day.

IReL plays a pivotal role in building Ireland’s scholarly infrastructure by embedding robust systems that support openness, transparency, and long-term sustainability. Central to this effort is the National Open Access Monitor, which provides comprehensive data on research outputs and enables evidence-based policy development. Alongside this, IReL advances the adoption of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) - such as ORCID iDs for researchers and DOIs for publications - ensuring that scholarship is uniquely identifiable, interoperable, and globally connected. Together, these initiatives create a resilient framework that empowers Irish researchers, enhances the visibility of their work, and strengthens Ireland’s position within the international scholarly communications landscape.

National Open Access Monitor

In March 2024, the National Open Research Forum (NORF), IReL and OpenAIRE jointly launched the pilot National Open Access Monitor, providing a cornerstone in Ireland’s move towards a fully open access research ecosystem. It has been very well received and welcomed by the Irish research community. The Monitor supports the shift towards transparency and accessibility of Irish research publications, and tracks Ireland’s goal of 100% of publicly funded research being open access by 2030.

The Monitor currently provides data on over: 595,000 publications, detailing publications from 2007 to the present day. It contains data on **1,290 Research Producing Organisations (RPOs)** and **143 Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)**. **47 RPO dashboard managers** and **21 RFO dashboard managers** have been registered and assigned.

The Monitor positions Ireland as a global leader in terms of implementing the UNESCO Open Science Recommendations.

Since the Monitor was launched in late 2022, we have held 22 information and training sessions, in addition to regular daily drop-in sessions to support participants. In recent months the focus of the Monitor, has been on supporting institutions to actively engage and use data from the Monitor. IReL and OpenAIRE are working directly with stakeholders to review their data and identify issues and improve accuracy in reporting. By making needed corrections to metadata and naming and affiliation attributions, a greater number of OA articles are being captured by the Monitor. We are currently working with six institutions and will roll this out to others in the coming months.

<https://oamonitor.ireland.openaire.eu/>

1,290
Research Producing Organisations (RPOs)

143
Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)

47
RPO dashboard managers

21
RFO dashboard managers

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

DataCite

IReL took over the role of Irish DataCite Consortium Lead Organisation from University College Dublin from 1st January 2024, and has been working on building Persistent Identifier (PID) adoption throughout the Irish research community.

In 2025, IReL welcomed three new members to Datacite: the Higher Education Authority (HEA), Teagasc and Technological University of the Shannon (TUS).

DataCite is a global community that shares a common interest: to ensure that research outputs and resources are openly available and connected so that their reuse can advance knowledge across and between disciplines, now and in the future.

The Higher Education Authority (HEA) has a statutory responsibility, at central government level, for the effective governance and regulation of higher education institutions and the higher education system, and Teagasc is the national body providing integrated research, advisory and training services to the agriculture and food industry and rural communities. TUS is a multi-campus university spread across seven campuses throughout Ireland's Midwest and Midlands region.

ORCID

ORCID is an international, interdisciplinary, open, non-proprietary, and not-for-profit organization created by the research community for the benefit of all stakeholders, including the organizations that support the research ecosystem.

ORCID consortia foster communities of practice that apply ORCID services and resources in regional and national contexts, using global implementation standards. The Irish ORCID consortium is part of a co-ordinated approach to the adoption and integration of ORCID in Ireland, directed by the Higher Education Authority. IReL is the lead organisation for the Irish ORCID consortium with Bridie O'Neill currently managing community and technical support for consortium members. The strategic agenda for the consortium is set by the IReL PID Advisory Committee.

Consortium membership is open to higher education, non-profit organizations, and government research and funding agencies located in and organized under the laws of Ireland.

PID Community Advisory Group

In 2025, IReL formed a new committee, the Persistent Identifiers (PID) Community Advisory Group. This committee supports the Irish scholarly community by advising IReL, the Irish DataCite Consortium, and the Irish ORCID Consortium on maximising the benefits of national adoption and use of DataCite and ORCID. Comprising members of the research and education sectors, the group complements Maynooth University's governance role as Consortia Lead and aligns with the obligations of the DataCite and ORCID consortium agreements.

Its advisory remit includes:

- Monitoring international trends and best practices;
- Identifying national and global opportunities for adoption;
- Recommending priorities for implementation.

The group also promotes the value of persistent identifiers and supports national coordination efforts, aligning with the NORF roadmap to accelerate uptake and integration. Using PIDs could save over:

“The IReL PID Community Advisory Group brings the Irish research community together to advise on and help drive the implementation of PIDs consistently and at scale. This national focus helps repositories, publishers, and funders embed DOIs, ORCID and other identifiers in everyday workflows. It is a practical approach to collective action for culture change.”

Dr. Cillian Joy, Head of Open and Digital Research, University of Galway

“IReL plays a vital role in supporting ORCID implementation and optimisation across Ireland, offering expert guidance on PURE-ORCID integration and creating spaces for collaboration through community events. These initiatives open up valuable opportunities for professionals to share best practices and engage with sector-wide developments.”

Through practical guidance, ongoing training programmes, and the cultivation of a vibrant national community of practice, IReL equips researchers and administrators at IADT to manage their ORCID profiles with confidence. This, in turn, enhances the visibility and interoperability of research outputs. What makes this work especially impactful is the approachable and knowledgeable IReL team including Bridie, Dolores, Jack, Susan, Aaron, and their colleagues, whose commitment is central to advancing Ireland's open research agenda and nurturing a resilient, collaborative research culture.”

Marie O'Neill, Professional Research Systems Officer, IADT

Data-Informed Decision-Making

IReL is evolving into a truly data-driven organisation, harnessing the power of the national Open Access (OA) monitor to chart the future of scholarly communications in Ireland. By systematically analysing trends and outputs, we gain the insight needed to align our strategies with the changing research landscape. This evidence-based approach informs our ongoing collection reviews, enabling us to identify gaps in services and resources with precision. In doing so, IReL strengthens its role as a national leader, ensuring that Irish researchers have access to the tools, publications, and infrastructures required to thrive in an open and connected scholarly ecosystem.

Scoping Future Opportunities: The 2025 Collections Review

Building on the insights from the 2024 IReL collections review - which assessed the usage, cost-effectiveness, and strategic alignment of currently licensed resources - this year's review focused on identifying potential opportunities for future expansion.

The central question guiding the 2025 review was: *Which publishers and resources should be considered for inclusion in future IReL agreements?* To explore this, we undertook a three-phase scoping exercise:

1: Analysis of Member Institutions' A-Z Database Listings

We examined common resources featured across institutional database pages to identify shared priorities.

Key findings:

- There was surprisingly little overlap between members. We interpret this positively as a sign that:
- IReL is fulfilling its role in licensing resources of common interest across the sector, while...
- allowing libraries to focus on resources of specific interest to their unique local community.

2: Member Survey on Desired Resources

Institutions were surveyed to gather input on additional resources they would like to see included in IReL's portfolio.

Key findings:

- There was significant interest in expanding the number of resources with publishers already included in IReL deals, or asking for a greater allocation of OA.
- We compiled a list of the top 3 resources requested by institutions.

3: Review of Publishing and Citation Activity

We analysed where IReL-affiliated authors are publishing and citing, focusing on publishers and publications not currently covered by existing agreements.

Key findings:

- IReL-members' paywalled articles rarely have a (discoverable) Green OA version.
- Researchers often publish Gold OA and cite papers outside of IReL deals.

This review was designed to inform strategic planning and future decision-making. It does not imply immediate changes to licensing arrangements, nor is there current funding allocated for new agreements in the short term.

About IReL

Governance Committee

Prof. Eeva Leinonen, Maynooth University, Chair
 Anna Lundén, National Library of Sweden
 Susan Reilly, IReL
 Dr. Kyle Adams, IReL, Secretary
 Sharon Bailey, University of Galway
 Coral Black, University College Cork
 Dr. Liam Brown, Technological University of the Shannon
 Allison Kavanagh, Technological University Dublin
 Cathal McCauley, Maynooth University
 Prof. Rachel Msetfi, Maynooth University
 Dr. Johanna Archbold, Atlantic Technological University

Advisory Committee

Dr. Brendan Jennings, Atlantic Technological University, Chair
 Monica Crump, University of Galway, Vice-chair
 Peter Brown, Research Ireland
 Arlene Healy, University College Dublin
 Ashling Hayes, University of Limerick
 Prof. Gianpiero Cavalleri, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland
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Negotiations Group

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 Dr. Richard Scriven, University College Cork
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National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group

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IReL Team Members

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 Aaron Binchy, Open Access Monitor Officer
 Dr. Catherine Ferris, Open Scholarship Officer
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Note on the Data

The data presented in this report covers the full calendar year from January to December 2024, as it was the most complete dataset available at the time of writing. However, the report also includes notable news items from both 2024 and 2025.